

INFLUENCE OF POVERTY AND ILLITERACY ON STREET KIDS IN UYO METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

The issue of street children represents a significant global social and environmental challenge, stemming from poverty, inadequate upbringing, neglect, and insufficient welfare for specific groups of children worldwide. This research focused on the influence of poverty and illiteracy on the rise of street children in the Uyo metropolis of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study utilized the Social Constructivism theory, as articulated by Lev Vygotsky, as its theoretical framework. A survey research design was employed for this investigation. Conducted in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, the study aimed for a sample size of 150, calculated using Taro Yamane's formula; however, only 120 questionnaires were successfully collected for data analysis. The data was analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), represented by 'r'. The results indicated that street children exist in a hostile environment, face neglect from the public, often lack adequate parental guidance and are particularly vulnerable to severe physical conditions, violence, harassment, exploitation, involvement in criminal activities, and denial of educational opportunities that could lead to improved life circumstances. In light of these findings, the researchers recommended that the government prioritize the development and execution of comprehensive social welfare programs aimed at tackling the underlying causes of child vulnerability. This should encompass initiatives to reduce poverty, enhance access to education and healthcare, provide affordable housing, and support families in crisis.

KEYWORDS: Poverty, illiteracy, Street kids, and Uyo

INTRODUCTION

The presence of street children in urban areas across Nigeria has evolved into a troubling issue in numerous cities. Currently, Nigeria is grappling with significant challenges related to national development and security. Many young individuals in the country navigate their lives without a clear moral compass, essential skills, or stable employment opportunities. The underlying cause of many societal problems in Nigeria stems from the disillusionment experienced by children and youth, resulting in a deterioration of ethical standards within our cities. These young people, who represent the nation's potential for productivity, are often compelled to engage in various forms of vagrancy to survive (Akpama, and Inaja, 2006).

A street kid is a term used for any child experiencing homelessness and lives on the street of a city, town or village. There is no definite definition of street kids, but many society, health practitioners and policymakers use UNICEF's definition of “any boys and girls, less than eighteen years, for whom “the street” (including unoccupied dwelling and wasteland) has become home and/or their source of livelihood, and who are inadequately protected or supervised, supervised or directed by responsible adults” (Aderinto, 2000). It therefore means that all children found on or on the street would fall into this category. Such children have been observed to spend more time on the street than at home.

In Nigeria, there is a particular type of street kids known as the “area boys and girls”. These kids are school drop-outs and are known to provide unsolicited security and also act as praise singers to envisaged successful individuals or political bigwigs living or passing through their “territories”. A study noted that these kids are at a high risk of getting involved in hard drugs or substance abuse which also increases the rate or level of violent crime in the city and society at large (Campbell and Ntsabane, 1995). Street kids are a common eyesore in major cities across the world but the problem is more prominent and rampant in developing and underdeveloped nations. Street kid challenge has gradually become an index capable of being used to measure the level of development in nations across the globe (Akpan and Oluabamide .2010).

In Akwa Ibom State these street kids are known as “Utoto or Nditouba” they are children experiencing homelessness and live on the streets of the city. Such children find ready-made homes in uncompleted or untenanted buildings, under bridges and wastelands in some cases. Some children perhaps are not homeless or without families, but live in environments where there is little or no protection or supervision from responsible adults. These kids feel that society, family, religion and most importantly government authorities have failed them because of the harsh conditions in which they find themselves. According to Akpama, and Inaja, (2006), the inability of families to perform their primary responsibility of taking care of their kids has led to the uncoordinated activities of children, these have led to children fleeing homes to fend for themselves on the streets, an act, which in turn has generated armies of children on the streets. Many of these kids have made the streets their homes out of frustration either because they were abandoned at birth, orphaned, or disowned by their parents who have branded them as witches or wizards or also outright neglected by their parents. However some children choose to live in the street out of defiance, peer pressure, poverty or due to the psychological makeup of their parents. Regrettably, some children are on the street to work and augment their family income. UNICEF categorized these street kids into two. “Children on the Street and Children of the Street” (UNICEF 2005).

Children on the street are those kids who have families and live with them but due to poverty and threat to their survival, are forced and exposed to the street to assume one role or the other in the street to hawk, beg, or engage in unskilled labours for a source of livelihood. While the “Children of the street are those kids who are in irredeemable positions and social dilemmas (Basu and Tzannatos, 2003). They have no home, may have no families to go back to, they are solely responsible for themselves; this may be due to crisis, death of parents, rejection and poverty. It is sad to note that these kids living on the streets are expected leaders of tomorrow going through all the dehumanizing experiences and unbearable frustrations which turn them against society (De Brito, 2014). The street stands for the public space and it is the place where children are not usually regarded, but life conditions drive some children to

carry out activities that determine their survival (Crosson, 2008). There are more street kids in poor, underdeveloped and developing countries whereas, the sight and population of street kids in developed countries are limited and under some relative control as a result of the citizen's welfare system of developed nations which at all times cater for and give attention and support to such children and their parents.

A recent study conducted in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, revealed that street children engaged in hawking could generate sales two to four times greater than adult traders operating from shops. Many of these children indicated that their mothers would struggle to provide food without the financial contributions they make from their daily hawking activities. Families facing financial hardship often lack the resources to adequately support their children, leading to a situation where children seek alternative means to obtain necessities for home or school. This has contributed to the growing presence of street children in the Uyo area. The current economic and social challenges have severely impacted the family unit's ability to fulfil its role in child-rearing. As a result of extreme hunger and insufficient parental guidance, many children are leaving their homes to survive on the streets, creating a significant population of youth in urban areas. This issue appears to be escalating and necessitates urgent intervention. In light of this context, the research examines the influence of poverty and illiteracy on the increasing number of street children in the Uyo metropolis.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Social Constructivism Theory

According to Lev Vygotsky (2015), a Russian Psychologist; social constructivism theory explains that learning in children occurs through social interactions and with the help of others. This theory emphasizes the role of social interactions and cultural context in shaping an individual's (child) understanding of the world. Social constructivism is a social learning theory which believes that individuals are active participants in the creation of their knowledge (Schreiber and Valle, 2013), Vygotsky believed that learning takes place primarily in social and cultural settings rather than solely within the individual. According to this theory; every function in the child's cultural development appears twice: first, on the social level 'between people' and later on, on the individual level 'inside the child'. Social constructivism theory focuses more on small groups. For instance, kids learn primarily through interactions with parents, peers and teachers, whereas teachers stimulate and facilitate conversations through connecting the natural flow of conversation.

The fundamental concept of Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism is the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which emphasizes on the role of the instructor in an individual's learning ability. In relating the theory to street kids, social constructivism suggests that their experiences and identities are socially constructed through their interactions with their environment, including institutions and cultural norms. According to the theory street kids are not destined to live on the streets, instead their situations are shaped by various social factors such as poverty, family dysfunction, abuse, neglect, or limited access to education and social support systems. These factors contribute to their marginalized status and can lead to their involvement in street life. The social constructivism theory postulates that street kid's behaviours', attitudes and survival strategies are influenced by the social contexts in which they find themselves. They may form peer groups and subcultures that

provides a sense of belonging and support within the street. They develop their own rules, norms and values which may differ from the mainstream society. Street kids may engage in activities such as begging, scavenging, hawking and other vices as a means of survival.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is located in the South-South geopolitical Zone of Nigeria, carved out from Cross River State in 1987 with its capital in Uyo and 31 Local Government Areas. The State is bordered on the East by Cross River State, on the West by Rivers State and Abia State, and on the South by the Atlantic Ocean. The state takes its name from the Qua Iboe River, which bisects the state before flowing into the Bight of Bonny. The population of the study comprised selected persons who are stakeholders in the street business in Uyo Metropolis. Two hundred and fifty (250) were selected.

The sample size of the study was determined from the population through the use of Taro Yamene's formula. The formula is given by equation 1:

Equation 1:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size (minimum)

N = population size

e = margin of error

I = constant

Thus n = unknown

$$N = 250$$

$$e = 0.05$$

$$= 1$$

$$\text{Thus : } n = 153.84 = 154$$

The main instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire constructed under the guidance of the supervisor. The instrument was divided into two parts (A and B). Considering the nature of data collected, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) denoted by 'r', was adopted by the researcher for data analysis. The PPMC was used in testing the research hypothesis to ascertain the significant relationships that exist between the identified variables. The model for 'r' is given as in equation 2:

Equation 2:

$$r = \frac{n\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{(n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}}$$

Where:

n = the number of observations or perceptions of the population

x = respondents rating of the significant relationship between the variable under consideration

y = the total of each of the options rated multiplied by free point Likert scaling

r = Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient

n = sample size

RESULT

Research Question: To what extent does poverty and illiteracy influence street kids in Uyo Metropolis?

Table 1: Percentage distribution of respondents' opinion on the extent to which poverty and illiteracy influences street kids in Uyo Metropolis.

S/N	Options	Frequency	Percentage %
1	Yes	67	55.83
2	No	47	39.16
3	Undecided	6	5
	Total	120	100

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork (2023)

From the above responses obtained as expressed in Table 1, 55.83% of the respondents believed that poverty which includes lack of food, clothes, shelter and illiteracy both on the part of the parents or guardians and the kids concerned contributes and influences the decision of kids to take to the streets; some of the kids are on the street to help their widowed mothers fend for their younger ones, others are on the street to make room for others, 39.16% of the respondents said no, while the remaining 5% were undecided.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In the cause of this research work it was discovered that many factors have forced kids out of their homes prominent among them is the loss of parents. Many of the kids on the streets of the Uyo metropolis have attributed their stay on the street to the loss of their parents. Many of them have been orphaned at a very tender age and have no one to care for, protect or supervise them; some of these kids were branded witches or wizards by their guardians.

Poverty and hunger were found to be other contributing factors to the menace of street kids. Poverty is the denial of choices and opportunities. According to Garcia, et al (2006), Nigeria's main challenge includes reducing poverty, diversifying its economy and improving healthcare. In the Uyo metropolis, widespread and severe poverty and hunger are a reality. Many of the kids on the street engage in hawking to contribute to the feeding of their younger siblings because their parents mostly mothers are unable to feed them.

CONCLUSION

The issue of street children within any community is fraught with numerous complex challenges that require significant attention from governmental bodies, civil society, and non-governmental organizations. This is crucial due to the profound implications it has on the broader society, particularly given that the prevailing portrayals of these children are often overwhelmingly negative. Research has indicated that economic factors like poverty and level of education for self-empowerment, which are particularly pronounced in underdeveloped or developing nations, play a significant role in the emergence of the street children phenomenon.

RECOMMENDATION

According to the findings of the study, the researcher recommend that the study area, Uyo metropolis, as a developing city, necessitates the implementation of effective policies aimed at addressing the issue of street kids, and facilitating the reintegration of those children who are already living on the streets back into mainstream society. The government must focus on the creation and execution of extensive social welfare programs designed to tackle the fundamental issues contributing to child vulnerability. This encompasses efforts to reduce poverty, ensure access to education and healthcare, offer affordable housing, and assist families facing crises.

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